

DEVELOPMENT OF NANOFIBERS REINFORCED POLYMER COMPOSITE FOR SPACE APPLICATION

H.M.S. Iqbal, S.Bhowmik, R.Benedictus
Faculty of Aerospace Engineering, Delft University of Technology
Kluyverweg 1, 2629 HS, Delft, The Netherlands
h.m.s.iqbal@tudelft.nl , s.bhowmik@tudelft.nl , R.benedictus@tudelft.nl

SUMMARY

In this study, efforts are made to develop carbon nanofibers (CNFs) reinforced Polybenzimidazol (PBI) nanocomposite to resist high energy radiations in harsh space environment. Thermal analysis shows that PBI has the highest glass transition temperature among high performance polymers and it has substantial thermal stability. Tensile test results show that neat PBI has very high tensile strength and Young's modulus. Improvement in thermal and mechanical properties is observed after the addition of 2% CNFs in the PBI polymer.

Keywords: Polybenzimidazole, carbon nanofibers, nano-composite, tensile testing, Glass transition

INTRODUCTION

Composite materials with excellent mechanical, thermal and fatigue properties, when applied to space structures reduces the overall cost of the mission [1]. Despite these positive aspects of utilizing composite materials, if the structures are required to operate for an extended period of time in space environment especially in low earth orbit (LEO), polymer matrix may have difficulty in maintaining the outstanding performance. So it is the need of the time to develop a polymer having high thermal and radiation resistance for extended period of time. Polybenzimidazol (PBI), a heterocyclic thermoplastic, with excellent thermal and chemical properties and outstanding mechanical properties [2] is one of the leading candidates for future aerospace applications. It has the highest glass transition temperature T_g (425 °C) of any commercial available organic polymer [2], high decomposition temperatures (500°- 600 °C), good oxidation resistance and it maintains excellent strength at cryogenic temperatures [3]. These properties make PBI an excellent candidate for aerospace applications. With the development of high performance polymers in recent years, extensive efforts are being made to incorporate nano-fibers to engineering polymers in order to further enhance their properties such as stiffness, toughness, thermal and barrier properties [4]. Based on these considerations, efforts are made to develop carbon nanofibers reinforced polymer composites.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials

The matrix used in this study was a solution of Polybenzimidazole (PBI) and DMAc (with 26% concentration of PBI) with an inherent viscosity of 0.75 supplied by PBI Performance Products. 99% concentrated N, N-Dimethylacetamide (DMAc) is purchased from Aldrich chemicals. Carbon nanofibres with diameter ranging from 70 nm to 200 nm and length

50 μm to 200 μm were supplied by Pyrograf Products, Inc. with trade name PR-19-XT-LHT. All materials were used as received.

Film Preparation

The as received solution of PBI in DMAc was very viscous and need to be diluted. 10 ml of DMAc was added to 20 gm of PBI solution and mechanically stirred at 50 °C for 15 minutes to get a uniform mixture of PBI in DMAc. The mixture was then used to fabricate 60 - 80 μm thick films. The films were prepared by spreading the mixture over the glass plate with the help of adjustable doctor blade which had micrometers to control the thickness of the film. The films were allowed to dry in the vacuum oven at 80 °C for 2 h and then it is cured at 200 °C for overnight. The cured film was peeled off from the glass plate by immersing in the hot distilled water at 80 °C. The film was again dried in the oven at 100 °C for 4 h to remove any moisture.

Preparation of Nano-composite

To fabricate the nano-composite film, carbon nanofibers (CNFs) were dispersed in the DMAc solution by ultrasonic mixing for 2 hours at 60 °C. After 2 hours of ultrasonic mixing, PBI solution was added to the CNFs. The ultrasonic process in combination with mechanical stirring was continued for next 1 hr. The mixture was then used to cast the film on the glass plate as described above. The nano-composite films were prepared with contents of 1 and 2 wt% of CNFs.

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) analysis

DSC analysis was carried out to determine glass transition temperature of both neat PBI and PBI nano-composites. Tests were performed using Perkins Elmer Thermal Analysis Instrument (Sapphire Differential Scanning Calorimeter). The samples were heated from 25 °C to 400 °C at a heating rate of 20 °C/min. The furnace was purged with nitrogen gas to prevent oxidation at a flow rate of 20 ml/min.

Thermal gravimetric analysis (TGA)

Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) was carried out to determine the thermal stability of neat polymer and nano-composite. Tests were performed using Perkins Elmer Thermal Analysis Instrument (Pyris Diamond Thermogravimetric Analyzer). The samples were heated from a temperature range of 25 °C to 550 °C at a heating rate of 10 °C/min. The furnace was purged with nitrogen gas to prevent oxidation at a flow rate of 25ml/min.

Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM)

Scanning electron microscope (SEM) analysis of nano-composite was carried out to examine the dispersion of carbon nanofibers. Images were obtained using JOUL JSM-7500F field emission scanning electron microscope (FE-SEM).

Tensile testing

Tensile testing of neat PBI film and carbon nanofibers reinforced PBI film was carried out using Zwick Tensile machine at test speed of 2 mm / min and 20 °C. Rectangular specimens of 150x10x0.06 (mm³) were cut from the casted films. Five specimens for all samples were tested. Force - displacement curves were recorded from which Young's

Modulus and tensile strength were evaluated. An extensometer was also used to determine the exact value of Young's Modulus.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) analysis

Differential Scanning Calorimetry analysis (DSC) was carried out to determine the physical properties of neat polymer and nano-composites. A comparison of DSC curves for neat polymer and nano-composite is shown in figure 1.

Figure 1 Comparison of DSC results for neat PBI and PBI nano-composites

Typical area of interest was to determine the glass transition temperature. No clear results were obtained for neat PBI and PBI with 2% CNFs. However, a small endothermic peak is observed around 360 °C for PBI reinforced with 1 % CNFs as shown in figure 1. This peak corresponds to the glass transition of the material. The glass transition temperature for PBI nano-composite is rather low than expected value. As polymer films fabricated from the solution of PBI in DMAc, so any DMAc left in the polymer film after getting it dried, has affected the glass transition temperature of the material.

Thermal gravimetric analysis (TGA)

Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) was carried out to determine the thermal stability of neat PBI and nano-composite. A comparison of TGA scan for neat PBI and PBI nano-composite is shown in figure 2.

Figure 2 Comparison of thermal stability of neat PBI and PBI nano-composites

TGA curve shows two steps degradation for neat PBI film. A relatively short degradation step started at about 50 °C and continued until a temperature of 200 °C with about 4% weight loss. The weight loss occurred is due to the moisture absorbed by the polymer and any DMAC remained inside the polymer film after getting it dried. After first degradation step, the polymer remained stable until the temperature of 410 °C with a total weight loss of 5% and thereafter, second degradation step started where weight loss occurred more rapidly but at the temperature of 550 °C, PBI was not totally degraded. Only 7% weight loss occurred up to this temperature. The high thermal stability of PBI is due to the presence of aromatic and heterocyclic ring in the polymer chain. At very high temperature, the weight loss takes place as ammonia and methane evolved from heterocyclic and aromatic ring respectively [5]. Addition of 1wt % of CNFs in PBI has not made much difference in the thermal stability of PBI. The TGA curve with very slight improvement has shifted upward. After addition of 2% carbon nanofibers in the polymer, it was observed that thermal stability of PBI has improved. The first step of degradation has almost eliminated as most of the moisture has been absorbed by CNFs. Only 1.5% weight loss occurred until a temperature of 200 °C and then polymer remained stable to a temperature of 430 °C and weight loss occurred was about 5%. Then the polymer started to degrade after this temperature.

Tensile testing

Tensile testing of neat PBI film and PBI nano-composite was carried to determine the effect of CNFs on tensile properties of PBI. Stress-strain curves for neat PBI and PBI nano-composite are shown in figure 3.

Figure 3 Comparison of Stress-Strain curves for neat PBI and PBI reinforced with 1% and 2% CNFs

A tensile strength of 151 MPa is achieved for neat PBI film which is the highest tensile strength of any of the high performance polymers. Further increase in strength is achieved by adding 1% and 2% CNFs in the polymer as shown in figure 3. 11% increase in tensile strength is achieved by dispersing 1% CNFs in the PBI. Both the stiffness and toughness of PBI has also increased. By adding CNFs up to 2 %, an increase in tensile strength is 23%

and value of Young's modulus has increased from 6.55 GPa to 8.10 GPa, an improvement of about 24% as shown in figure 4.

Figure 4 Comparison of Young's Modulus with different contents of CNFs in PBI

An improvement of 45% in failure strain is also achieved by adding 2 % CNFs in PBI polymer. In general, filler additions are detrimental to the toughness of the material. However, it is interesting to see that addition of carbon nanofibers has improved the toughness of PBI. This kind of effect of CNFs on the toughness of the polymer has also been reported by some other researchers [6, 7].

Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) Analysis

Scanning electron microscope (SEM) analysis of neat PBI and PBI nano-composite was carried out to examine the dispersion of carbon nanofibers. Figure 5c and 5d are the SEM photographs of 1% and 2% nano-composites films respectively, showing uniform dispersion of the CNFs within PBI matrix.

Figure 5 SEM analysis of (a) Neat PBI x1000 (b) Neat PBI X10000 (c) PBI-1CNF x 5000 (d) PBI – 2CNF x3000

Conclusions

PBI nano-composite films containing 1 and 2 wt% CNFs were fabricated using PBI solution. The effect of CNF additions on thermal and mechanical properties of PBI was studied. TGA analysis showed that thermal stability of PBI has improved by adding 2 wt% of CNFs. Tensile test results showed that the tensile strength and Young's modulus of PBI were improved considerably by adding only 2 wt% of CNF. Furthermore, CNF additions improved toughness of PBI. SEM analysis of PBI reinforced with 2% CNFs showed that CNFs were dispersed uniformly in PBI polymer. These results end up with the conclusion that PBI is a high performance polymer with excellent thermal and mechanical properties and these properties can be further enhanced by uniform dispersion of CNFs in PBI. These properties make PBI an excellent candidate for aerospace applications.

References

- [1] Joo-Hyun Han, Chun-Gon Kim, *Composite Structures* 72 (2006) 218–226
- [2] Paul A. Steiner and Robert Sandor, *High performance polymers*, 1991; 3; 139
- [3] S. Bhowmik, H. W. Bonin, V. T. Bui, R. D. Weir, Wiley InterScience, 2006
- [4] Gojny, F.H., Wichmann, M.H.G., Fiedler, B., Schulte, K, *Comp. Sci. & Tech.*, Vol. 65, pp.2300-2313, 2005.
- [5] D.A.Chatfield and I.N.Einhorn, *J. polym. Sci*, 19 (1981) 601
- [6] S.P. Bao, S.C. Tjong, Wiley InterScience, *POLYMER COMPOSITES*, 2008
- [7] Y.J. Shi, X. Feng, H.Y. Wang, X.H. Lu, and J.Y. Shen, *J. Appl. Polym. Sci*, 104, 2430 (2007)